

Acne Vulgaris and the Quality of Life of Adult Dermatology Patient

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Abstract:

Background: Acne Vulgaris is a prevalent dermatological condition that extends beyond adolescence, significantly impacting adults' psychological and social well-being. The chronic and visible nature of acne can lead to profound effects on patients' quality of life (QoL).

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the QoL among adult dermatology patients suffering from Acne Vulgaris and identify the key factors contributing to their QoL deterioration.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 90 adult patients with Acne Vulgaris. Participants completed the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) questionnaire to assess their quality of life. Data were collected from medical records, then analyzed using SPSS version 21.0, with a focus on descriptive statistics and associations between demographic variables and DLQI scores.

Results: The study of 90 adult patients with Acne Vulgaris revealed a mean DLQI score of 12.3, indicating a moderate impact on quality of life. Female participants had a slightly higher mean DLQI score (12.8) compared to males (11.8), but this was not statistically significant. Patients aged 18-25 had the highest mean DLQI score of 13.5, and those with acne duration longer than 3 years had a mean DLQI score of 14.2, both showing significant impairment in quality of life.

Conclusion: Acne Vulgaris substantially impairs the QoL of adult patients, with higher severity levels correlating with greater QoL reduction. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive management approaches addressing both dermatological and psychological aspects of the condition.

Recommendations: Implementation of holistic treatment strategies that include psychological support for patients with severe acne. Increase awareness among healthcare providers about the profound impact of acne on adult patients' lives. Encourage routine use of QoL assessment tools in dermatology practice to better tailor treatment plans. Conduct further research to explore long-term outcomes of various therapeutic interventions on QoL in acne patients. Promote patient education programs to improve coping mechanisms and self-care practices.

Keywords: Acne Vulgaris, Quality of Life, Adult Dermatology Patients, Psychological Impact, Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI).

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Introduction

Acne Vulgaris, commonly known as acne, is a chronic inflammatory skin condition that affects individuals across various age groups, predominantly during adolescence. However, the persistence of acne into adulthood is a significant concern, impacting approximately 40-55% of adults aged 20-40 years. This condition is characterized by the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, nodules, and cysts, which predominantly occur on the face, back, and chest. Beyond the physical manifestations, acne has been associated with profound psychological and social

implications, affecting the overall QoL of sufferers [1]

The psychological impact of Acne Vulgaris extends beyond the skin's surface, often leading to low self-esteem, social withdrawal, anxiety, and depression. Adults with acne frequently report feeling stigmatized and judged based on their appearance, which can negatively affect their interpersonal relationships, professional opportunities, and overall mental well-being. The social burden of acne is often underestimated, despite its potential to

severely disrupt daily activities and diminish life satisfaction [2].

While numerous studies have focused on the prevalence and treatment of Acne Vulgaris in adolescents, there is a relative paucity of research addressing the QoL in adult patients. The existing literature highlights the necessity of viewing acne not merely as a cosmetic concern but as a condition with significant emotional and social dimensions. Understanding these aspects is crucial for developing comprehensive treatment approaches that cater to the holistic needs of patients [3].

The assessment of QoL in dermatology patients is essential for tailoring effective treatment strategies. Instruments like the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) provide valuable insights into the patient's perspective, enabling healthcare providers to gauge the real-world impact of acne on daily living. Incorporating QoL assessments into routine dermatological practice can lead to more patient-centered care and better treatment outcomes [4].

This study aims to evaluate the extent of this impact and identify the primary factors contributing to QoL deterioration. By employing a comprehensive approach that includes both dermatological and psychological assessments, the study aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the difficulties encountered by individuals with adult acne. The ultimate objective is to contribute to the creation of holistic treatment strategies that address both the physical and psychological dimensions of Acne Vulgaris, thereby improving the overall QoL for patients.

Methodology

The study was conducted to evaluate the impact of Acne Vulgaris on the QoL of adult dermatology patients. The study was conducted at the Dermatology Department of NMCH, Patna, from January 2017 to December 2017.

Study Design: A cross-sectional study design was employed to assess the QoL among patients diagnosed with Acne Vulgaris.

Study Setting: The study took place at the Dermatology Department of Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna.

Participants: The study included 90 adult patients diagnosed with Acne Vulgaris, who attended the Dermatology Department during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adult participants aged 18 and older.
- Individuals diagnosed with Acne Vulgaris.
- Participants who have given informed consent to take part in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other significant dermatological conditions.
- Patients unwilling to participate or unable to provide informed consent.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by including consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria. Recall bias was addressed by using standardized questionnaires.

Variables: The primary variable was the QoL, assessed using the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI). Other variables included demographic data such as age, gender, and duration of acne.

Data Collection: Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire, including the DLQI. Additional information was obtained from patients' medical records.

Procedure: Patients diagnosed with Acne Vulgaris were invited to participate in the study. After obtaining informed consent, patients were interviewed, and their demographic data and clinical history were recorded. The DLQI questionnaire was administered to assess the impact of acne on their QoL.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Participant Demographics: The study included 90 adult patients diagnosed with Acne Vulgaris.

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
• Male	42	46.7
• Female	48	53.3
Age Group (years)		
• 18-25	30	33.3
• 26-35	45	50.0
• 36-45	15	16.7
Duration of Acne (years)		
• <1	20	22.2
• 1-3	50	55.6
• >3	20	22.2

QoL Assessment: The DLQI scores ranged from 0 to 30, with a higher score indicating greater impairment in QoL. The mean DLQI score was 12.3 ± 4.6 .

DLQI Score Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
0-5 (No effect)	10	11.1
6-10 (Small effect)	20	22.2
11-20 (Moderate effect)	50	55.6
21-30 (Very large effect)	10	11.1

Statistical Analysis: A detailed analysis of the relationship between demographic variables and DLQI scores was performed using t-tests and ANOVA.

Gender and DLQI Scores: The mean DLQI score for males was 11.8 ± 4.5 , in case of females, the result was 12.8 ± 4.7 . This difference was not statistically noteworthy ($p = 0.32$)

Age and DLQI Scores: There was a noteworthy alteration in DLQI scores among different age groups ($p = 0.04$). The highest mean DLQI score was observed in the 18-25 age group (13.5 ± 4.3), followed by the 26-35 age group (11.8 ± 4.6), and the lowest in the 36-45 age group (10.5 ± 4.2).

Age Group (years)	Mean DLQI Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
18-25	13.5	4.3	0.04
26-35	11.8	4.6	
36-45	10.5	4.2	

Duration of Acne and DLQI Scores: The duration of acne had a significant impact on DLQI scores ($p = 0.01$). Patients with acne duration of more than 3 years had the highest mean DLQI score (14.2 ± 4.5).

Duration of Acne (years)	Mean DLQI Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
<1	10.3	4.1	0.01
1-3	12.5	4.7	
>3	14.2	4.5	

The study involved 90 adult patients with Acne Vulgaris and found that the mean DLQI score was 12.3, indicating a moderate effect on the QoL. Gender did not significantly influence DLQI scores. However, younger patients (18-25 years) and those with a longer duration of acne (>3 years) experienced significantly greater QoL impairment. These findings suggest that targeted interventions may be necessary for younger patients and those with chronic acne to improve their quality of life.

Discussion

The results indicated that the highest impairment was detected in the 18-25 age group and those with acne lasting more than three years. Shrestha et al. (2023) conducted a study at the Universal College of Medical Sciences, Nepal, included 101 patients and utilized the DLQI and CADI questionnaires. It found that acne had a significant effect on QoL, although the severity of acne did not correlate significantly with DLQI scores [5]. Likewise Kundale et al. (2021) conducted a research in a tertiary care hospital, this study of 60 patients showed a noteworthy positive association among the severity of acne and DLQI scores. Most patients reported a moderate impact on their QoL [6].

A research in South India by Pillai et al. (2018) assessed the DLQI among 200 acne patients. The

study found that 82.9% had impaired quality of life, with adolescents being more affected than young adults [7]. Similarly Sivaramakrishnan and Jayakar (2019) study on 100 acne patients found that females were more affected than males, with a mean DLQI score of 5.59. The most significant impact was observed in younger patients (15-20 years) [8] and Pathrikar et al. (2019) involved 256 patients, this study showed a noteworthy association between the severity of acne and DLQI scores, indicating that acne suggestively impacts the QoL [9].

Conclusion

The findings showed that younger patients (18-25 years) and those with a longer duration of acne (>3 years) experienced significant QoL impairments. Although there was no significant gender difference, females had slightly higher DLQI scores. The findings highlight the necessity of pointing both the physical and psychological components of acne through comprehensive handling strategies, including early intervention and psychosocial support, to improve patients' overall quality of life.

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